

**SOME CONGRUENCES FOR (S, T) -REGULAR BIPARTITIONS
MODULO T**

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Abstract

In this work, we study the function $B_{s,t}(n)$, which counts the number of (s, t) -regular bipartitions of n . Recently, many authors proved the existence of infinite families of congruences modulo 11 for $B_{3,11}(n)$, modulo 3 for $B_{3,s}(n)$ and modulo 5 for $B_{5,s}(n)$. Most recently, the first author proved the existence of infinite families of congruences modulo 11, 13 and 17 for $B_{5,11}(n)$, $B_{5,13}(n)$ and $B_{81,17}(n)$, respectively. In this paper, we establish the existence of infinite families of congruences modulo 5 for $B_{2,15}(n)$, modulo 11 for $B_{7,11}(n)$, modulo 11 for $B_{27,11}(n)$ and modulo 17 for $B_{243,17}(n)$.

1. Introduction

For a positive integer n , a *partition* of n is a non-increasing sequence of positive integers whose sum is n . The number of partitions of n is denoted by $p(n)$. The generating function for $p(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(n)q^n = \frac{1}{(q; q)_{\infty}}. \quad (1)$$

For a non-zero integer k , we define the general partition function $p_k(n)$ as the coefficient of q^n in the expansion of $(q; q)_{\infty}^k$. If $k = -1$, then we have the usual partition function $p(n)$. The generating function for $p_k(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_k(n)q^n = (q; q)_{\infty}^k, \quad (2)$$

where, as usual,

$$f_k := (q^k; q^k)_\infty = \prod_{m=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{mk}).$$

In [18, 20], Ramanujan obtained the significant identities

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(5n + 4)q^n = 5 \frac{f_5^5}{f_1^6} \tag{3}$$

and

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(7n + 5)q^n = 7 \frac{f_7^3}{f_1^4} + 49q \frac{f_7^7}{f_1^8}. \tag{4}$$

Ramanujan [18] gave a brief proof of (3). He did not prove (4) in [18], but he did give a sketch of his proof of (4) in his unpublished manuscript on the partition and τ -functions [19]. Note that (3) and (4) immediately yield the congruences $p(5n + 4) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ and $p(7n + 5) \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$.

Ramanujan’s partition congruences motivated an investigation of many classes of partitions, such as ℓ -regular partitions. For a positive integer ℓ , a partition is said to be ℓ -regular if none of its parts is divisible by ℓ . Let $b_\ell(n)$ denote the number of ℓ -regular partitions of n . The generating function for $b_\ell(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_\ell(n)q^n = \frac{f_\ell}{f_1}. \tag{5}$$

The arithmetic properties of ℓ -regular partitions have been extensively studied in recent years. Some of the references are [5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 13, 22, 23, 25].

A bipartition (λ, μ) of n is a pair of partitions (λ, μ) such that the sum of all the parts of λ and μ equals n . A (s, t) -regular bipartition of n is a bipartition (λ, μ) of n such that λ is an s -regular partition and μ is a t -regular partition. Let $B_{s,t}(n)$ denote the number of (s, t) -regular bipartitions of n . If $s = t$, then we denote $B_{s,t}(n)$ as $B_s(n)$ for simplicity. The generating function of $B_{s,t}(n)$ is given by

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{s,t}(n)q^n = \frac{f_s f_t}{f_1^2}. \tag{6}$$

Recently, Lin [16] proved the existence of infinite families of congruences modulo 3 for $B_7(n)$, by using Ramanujan’s two modular equations of degree 7, and in [17] he proved the existence of infinite families of congruences modulo 3 for $B_{13}(n)$. For more related works, see [15, 21].

In a recent paper, Dou [8] proved that for $n \geq 0$ and $\alpha \geq 2$,

$$B_{3,11} \left(3^\alpha n + \frac{5 \cdot 3^{\alpha-1} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{11}.$$

Adiga and Ranganatha [1] proved the existence of infinite families of congruences modulo 3 for $B_{3,7}(n)$, and Xia and Yao [24] proved the existence of infinite families of congruences modulo 3 for $B_{3,s}(n)$, modulo 5 for $B_{5,s}(n)$ and modulo 7 for $B_{3,7}(n)$. Let us consider an example. For a positive integer s , non-negative integer n and a prime $p \geq 5$,

$$B_{3,s} \left(p^{2\alpha+1}n + \frac{(1+s)(p^{2\alpha+2}-1)}{24} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}.$$

Most recently, the first author [14] proved the existence of infinite families of congruences modulo 11, 13 and 17 for $B_{5,11}(n)$, $B_{5,13}(n)$ and $B_{81,17}(n)$, respectively. For example, for all $n \geq 0$ and $m \geq 0$,

$$B_{5,13} \left(5^{6m+5}(5n+k) + \frac{5^{6m+5}-2}{3} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{13}, \text{ where } k \in \{1, 5\}.$$

In this paper, we prove the existence of infinite families of congruences modulo 5, 11, 11 and 17 for $B_{2,15}(n)$, $B_{7,11}(n)$, $B_{27,11}(n)$ and $B_{243,17}(n)$, respectively. The following are the main results in this paper.

Theorem 1. For all $n \geq 0$ and $m \geq 0$,

$$B_{2,15} \left(3^{2m+1}n + \frac{7 \cdot 3^{2m+1} - 5}{8} \right) \equiv 2^m B_{2,15}(3n+2) \pmod{5}, \tag{7}$$

$$B_{2,15} \left(3^{2m+2}n + \frac{23 \cdot 3^{2m+1} - 5}{8} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \tag{8}$$

$$B_{2,15} \left(3^{2(m+1)+1}n + \frac{13 \cdot 3^{2(m+1)} - 5}{8} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}. \tag{9}$$

Theorem 2. For all $n \geq 0$ and $m \geq 0$,

$$B_{7,11} \left(7^{12m}n + \frac{2 \cdot 7^{12m} - 2}{3} \right) \equiv 3^m B_{7,11}(n) \pmod{11}, \tag{10}$$

$$B_{7,11} \left(7^{12m+11}(7n+k) + \frac{2 \cdot 7^{12m+11} - 2}{3} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{11}, \tag{11}$$

where $k \in \{1, 5, 6\}$.

Theorem 3. For all $n \geq 0$ and $m \geq 4$,

$$B_{27,11} \left(3^m n + \frac{5 \cdot 3^{m-1} - 3}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{11}. \tag{12}$$

Theorem 4. For all $n \geq 0$,

$$B_{243,17}(81n+23) \equiv 0 \pmod{17}, \tag{13}$$

$$B_{243,17}(81n+77) \equiv 0 \pmod{17}. \tag{14}$$

2. The Identities

In this section, we prove some lemmas to prove our main results. For any prime p , by using binomial theorem, we have

$$f_p \equiv f_1^p \pmod{p}. \tag{15}$$

Let us recall the results due to Berndt [2], Hirschhorn [11], and Hirschhorn and Sellers [12].

Lemma 1 (Berndt [2, p. 49]). We have

$$\frac{f_2^2}{f_1} = \frac{f_6 f_9^2}{f_3 f_{18}} + q \frac{f_{18}^2}{f_9}. \tag{16}$$

Lemma 2 (Hirschhorn [11, Eqs. (21.3.1), (22.1.4) and (39.2.8)]). We have

$$f_1^3 = a(q^3) f_3 - 3q f_9^3, \tag{17}$$

$$a(q) = a(q^3) + 6q \frac{f_9^3}{f_3}, \tag{18}$$

$$\frac{1}{f_1^3} = a^2(q^3) \frac{f_9^3}{f_3^{10}} + 3qa(q^3) \frac{f_9^6}{f_3^{11}} + 9q^2 \frac{f_9^9}{f_3^{12}}, \tag{19}$$

where

$$a(q) = \sum_{m,n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{m^2+mn+n^2}.$$

Lemma 3 (Hirschhorn and Sellers [12]). We have

$$\frac{f_2}{f_1^2} = \frac{f_6^4 f_9^6}{f_3^8 f_{18}^3} + 2q \frac{f_6^3 f_9^3}{f_3^7} + 4q^2 \frac{f_6^2 f_{18}^3}{f_3^6}. \tag{20}$$

Lemma 4. For $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_5(7n+3)q^n = 10f_1^4 f_7 + 49q f_7^5. \tag{21}$$

Proof. Setting $k = 5$ in (2), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_5(n)q^n = f_1^5. \tag{22}$$

In [2, p. 303, Entry 17(v)], we have

$$f_1 = f_{49} \left(\frac{B(q^7)}{C(q^7)} - \frac{A(q^7)}{B(q^7)} q - q^2 + \frac{C(q^7)}{A(q^7)} q^5 \right), \tag{23}$$

where A , B and C are defined by

$$A = A(q) := \frac{f(-q^3, -q^4)}{f(-q^2)}, \quad B = B(q) := \frac{f(-q^2, -q^5)}{f(-q^2)} \quad \text{and} \quad C = C(q) := \frac{f(-q, -q^6)}{f(-q^2)}.$$

Substituting (23) into (22), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_5(n)q^n = f_{49}^5 \left(\frac{B(q^7)}{C(q^7)} - \frac{A(q^7)}{B(q^7)}q - q^2 + \frac{C(q^7)}{A(q^7)}q^5 \right)^5. \tag{24}$$

If we extract those terms in which the power of q is congruent to 3 modulo 7, dividing by q^3 and replacing q^7 by q , then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_5(7n + 3)q^n &= f_7^5 \left(20 \left(\frac{AB^2}{C^3} + \frac{A^2Cq}{B^3} - \frac{BC^2q^2}{A^3} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 10 \left(\frac{A^3}{BC^2} - \frac{B^3q}{A^2C} - \frac{C^3q^2}{AB^2} \right) - 61q \right). \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

From [3, p. 174, Entry 31] and [4, Eq. 3.11 and Eq. 3.15] in the terms of A , B and C , we have

$$\frac{B^5}{AC^4} - \frac{A^5}{B^4C} - \frac{C^5q^3}{A^4B} = 3q, \tag{26}$$

$$\frac{AB^2}{C^3} + \frac{A^2Cq}{B^3} - \frac{BC^2q^2}{A^3} = \frac{f_1^4}{f_7^4} + 8q, \tag{27}$$

$$\frac{A^3}{BC^2} - \frac{B^3q}{A^2C} - \frac{C^3q^2}{AB^2} = \frac{f_1^4}{f_7^4} + 5q, \tag{28}$$

$$\frac{B^7}{C^7} - \frac{A^7q}{B^7} + \frac{C^7q^5}{A^7} = \frac{f_1^8}{f_7^8} + 14q \frac{f_1^4}{f_7^4} + 57q^2. \tag{29}$$

Substituting (27) and (28) into (25), and simplifying, completes the proof of Lemma 4. □

Lemma 5. For $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(7n + 4)q^n = -90f_1^8f_7 - 882qf_1^4f_7^5 - 2401q^2f_7^9. \tag{30}$$

Proof. Setting $k = 9$ in (2), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(n)q^n = f_1^9. \tag{31}$$

Substituting (23) into (31), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(n)q^n = f_{49}^9 \left(\frac{B(q^7)}{C(q^7)} - \frac{A(q^7)}{B(q^7)}q - q^2 + \frac{C(q^7)}{A(q^7)}q^5 \right)^9. \tag{32}$$

If we extract those terms in which the power of q is congruent to 4 modulo 7, dividing by q^4 and replacing q^7 by q , then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(7n+4)q^n &= f_7^9 \left(\left(\frac{36B^7}{C^7} - \frac{252A^2B^4}{C^6} + \frac{126A^4B}{C^5} \right) \right. \\ &\quad + q \left(-\frac{36A^7}{B^7} + \frac{756A^5}{B^4C} - \frac{3780A^3}{BC^2} - \frac{756B^5}{AC^4} + \frac{4284AB^2}{C^3} \right) \\ &\quad + q^2 \left(-\frac{252A^4C^2}{B^6} + \frac{4284A^2C}{B^3} + \frac{3780B^3}{A^2C} - 9745 \right) \\ &\quad + q^3 \left(\frac{126B^4C}{A^5} - \frac{4284BC^2}{A^3} - \frac{126AC^4}{B^5} + \frac{3780C^3}{AB^2} \right) \\ &\quad \left. + q^4 \left(\frac{756C^5}{A^4B} - \frac{252B^2C^4}{A^6} \right) + \frac{36C^7}{A^7} q^5 \right). \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

On rearranging the equation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(7n+4)q^n &= f_7^9 \left(36 \left(\frac{B^7}{C^7} - \frac{A^7q}{B^7} + \frac{C^7q^5}{A^7} \right) \right. \\ &\quad - 252 \left(\frac{A^2B^4}{C^6} - \frac{A^4C^2q^2}{B^6} - \frac{B^2C^4q^4}{A^6} \right) + 126 \left(\frac{A^4B}{C^5} + \frac{B^4Cq^3}{A^5} - \frac{AC^4q^3}{B^5} \right) \\ &\quad - 756q \left(\frac{B^5}{AC^4} - \frac{A^5}{B^4C} - \frac{C^5q^3}{A^4B} \right) + 4284q \left(\frac{AB^2}{C^3} + \frac{A^2Cq}{B^3} - \frac{BC^2q^2}{A^3} \right) \\ &\quad \left. - 3780q \left(\frac{A^3}{BC^2} - \frac{B^3q}{A^2C} - \frac{C^3q^2}{AB^2} \right) - 9745q^2 \right). \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

From the above equation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(7n+4)q^n &= 36f_7^9 \left(\frac{B^7}{C^7} - \frac{A^7q}{B^7} + \frac{C^7q^5}{A^7} \right) \\ &\quad - 252f_7^9 \left(\left(\frac{AB^2}{C^3} + \frac{A^2Cq}{B^3} - \frac{BC^2q^2}{A^3} \right)^2 - 2q \left(\frac{A^3}{BC^2} - \frac{B^3q}{A^2C} - \frac{C^3q^2}{AB^2} \right) \right) \\ &\quad + 126f_7^9 \left(q \left(\frac{B^5}{AC^4} - \frac{A^5}{B^4C} - \frac{C^5q^3}{A^4B} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(\frac{AB^2}{C^3} + \frac{A^2Cq}{B^3} - \frac{BC^2q^2}{A^3} \right) \left(\frac{A^3}{BC^2} - \frac{B^3q}{A^2C} - \frac{C^3q^2}{AB^2} \right) \right) \\ &\quad - 756qf_7^9 \left(\frac{B^5}{AC^4} - \frac{A^5}{B^4C} - \frac{C^5q^3}{A^4B} \right) + 4284qf_7^9 \left(\frac{AB^2}{C^3} + \frac{A^2Cq}{B^3} - \frac{BC^2q^2}{A^3} \right) \\ &\quad - 3780qf_7^9 \left(\frac{A^3}{BC^2} - \frac{B^3q}{A^2C} - \frac{C^3q^2}{AB^2} \right) - 9367q^2f_7^9. \end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

Substituting (26), (27), (28) and (29) into (35), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(7n+4)q^n \\ &= 36f_7^9 \left(\frac{f_1^8}{f_7^8} + 14q \frac{f_1^4}{f_7^4} + 57q^2 \right) - 252f_7^9 \left(\left(\frac{f_1^4}{f_7^4} + 8q \right)^2 - 2q \left(\frac{f_1^4}{f_7^4} + 5q \right) \right) \\ & \quad + 126f_7^9 \left((3q) + \left(\frac{f_1^4}{f_7^4} + 5q \right) \left(\frac{f_1^4}{f_7^4} + 8q \right) \right) - 756qf_7^9(3q) \\ & \quad + 4284qf_7^9 \left(\frac{f_1^4}{f_7^4} + 8q \right) - 3780qf_7^9 \left(\frac{f_1^4}{f_7^4} + 5q \right) - 9367q^2 f_7^9. \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

Simplifying Equation (36) completes the proof. □

3. Congruence for (2, 15)-regular Bipartition

Theorem 5. *For $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$B_{2,15}(9n+8) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \tag{37}$$

$$B_{2,15}(27n+14) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \tag{38}$$

$$B_{2,15}(27n+23) \equiv 2B_{2,15}(3n+2) \pmod{5}. \tag{39}$$

Proof. Setting $s = 2$, and $t = 15$ in (6), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{2,15}(n)q^n = \frac{f_2 f_{15}}{f_1^2}. \tag{40}$$

Substituting (20) into (40), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{2,15}(n)q^n = f_{15} \left(\frac{f_6^4 f_9^6}{f_3^8 f_{18}^3} + 2q \frac{f_6^3 f_9^3}{f_3^7} + 4q^2 \frac{f_6^2 f_{18}^3}{f_3^6} \right). \tag{41}$$

If we extract those terms in which the power of q is congruent to 2 modulo 3, dividing by q^2 and replacing q^3 by q , then we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{2,15}(3n+2)q^n \equiv 4 \frac{f_2^2 f_6^3}{f_1} \pmod{5}. \tag{42}$$

Substituting (16) into (42), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{2,15}(3n+2)q^n \equiv 4f_6^3 \left(\frac{f_6 f_9^2}{f_3 f_{18}} + q \frac{f_{18}^2}{f_9} \right) \pmod{5}. \tag{43}$$

If we extract those terms in which the power of q is congruent to 1 modulo 3, dividing by q and replacing q^3 by q , then we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{2,15}(9n+5)q^n \equiv 4 \frac{f_6^2 f_2^3}{f_3} \pmod{5}. \tag{44}$$

Now replacing q by q^2 in (17), we have

$$f_2^3 = f_6 a(q^6) - 3q^2 f_{18}^3. \tag{45}$$

Substituting (45) into (44), extracting those terms in which the power of q is congruent to 2 modulo 3, dividing by q^2 and replacing q^3 by q , we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{2,15}(27n+23)q^n \equiv 3 \frac{f_2^2 f_6^3}{f_1} \pmod{5}. \tag{46}$$

Substituting (45) into (44), extracting those terms in which the power of q is congruent to 1 modulo 3, dividing by q and replacing q^3 by q , we have (38). This completes the proof of Theorem 5, which follows from (43) and (46). $\square$

Next, we give a proof of Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. By mathematical induction, Congruence (7) follows from (39). Employing (37) and (38) in (7), we obtain (8) and (9).

4. Congruence for (7, 11)-regular Bipartition

We now present a proof of Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 2. Setting $s = 7$, and $t = 11$ in (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(n)q^n &\equiv f_7 f_1^9 \pmod{11} \\ &\equiv f_7 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(n)q^n \pmod{11}. \end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

It follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(7n+4)q^n \equiv f_1 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(7n+4)q^n \pmod{11}. \tag{48}$$

Now from (30) and (48), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(7n+4)q^n &\equiv f_1 (9f_1^8 f_7 + 9q f_1^4 f_7^5 + 8q^2 f_7^9) \\ &\equiv 9f_7 f_1^9 + 9q f_7^5 f_1^5 + 8q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}. \end{aligned} \tag{49}$$

Substituting (22), (23) and (31) into (49), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(7n+4)q^n &\equiv 9f_7 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(n)q^n + 9f_7^5 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_5(n)q^{n+1} \\ &\quad + 8q^2 f_7^9 f_{49} \left(\frac{B(q^7)}{C(q^7)} - \frac{A(q^7)}{B(q^7)} q - q^2 + \frac{C(q^7)}{A(q^7)} q^5 \right) \pmod{11}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(49n+32)q^n \equiv 9f_1 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_9(7n+4)q^n + 9f_1^5 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p_5(7n+3)q^n + 3f_1^9 f_7 \pmod{11}. \tag{50}$$

Substituting Lemma 4 and Lemma 5 into (50), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(49n+32)q^n &\equiv 9f_1 (9f_1^8 f_7 + 9qf_1^4 f_7^5 + 8q^2 f_7^9) + 9f_1^5 (10f_1^4 f_7 + 5qf_7^5) \\ &\quad + 3f_1^9 f_7 \\ &\equiv 9f_7 f_1^9 + 5qf_7^5 f_1^5 + 6q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}. \end{aligned} \tag{51}$$

Similarly, we find

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(343n+228)q^n &\equiv 4f_7 f_1^9 + 7qf_7^5 f_1^5 + 6q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(2401n+1600)q^n &\equiv f_7 f_1^9 + 5qf_7^5 f_1^5 + 10q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(16807n+11204)q^n &\equiv 5f_7 f_1^9 + qf_7^5 f_1^5 + 8q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(117649n+78432)q^n &\equiv 3f_7 f_1^9 + 6qf_7^5 f_1^5 + 7q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(823543n+549028)q^n &\equiv 3f_7 f_1^9 + 2qf_7^5 f_1^5 + 2q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(5764801n+3843200)q^n &\equiv f_7 f_1^9 + 4qf_7^5 f_1^5 + 2q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(40353607n+26902404)q^n &\equiv 3f_7 f_1^9 + 7qf_7^5 f_1^5 + 8q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(282475249n+188316832)q^n &\equiv f_7 f_1^9 + 7qf_7^5 f_1^5 + 2q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}, \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11}(1977326743n+1318217828)q^n &\equiv 8q^2 f_7^9 f_1 \pmod{11}. \end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

Substituting (23) into (52), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{7,11} \left(7^{11}n + \frac{2(7^{11} - 1)}{3} \right) q^n \equiv 8q^2 f_7^9 f_{49} \left(\frac{B(q^7)}{C(q^7)} - \frac{A(q^7)}{B(q^7)} q - q^2 + \frac{C(q^7)}{A(q^7)} q^5 \right). \tag{53}$$

There are no terms on the right of q^{7n+1} , q^{7n+5} and q^{7n+6} , so

$$B_{7,11} \left(7^{11}(7n + k) + \frac{2(7^{11} - 1)}{3} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{11}, \text{ where } k = 1, 5, 6. \tag{54}$$

and

$$B_{7,11} \left(7^{12}n + \frac{2(7^{12} - 1)}{3} \right) \equiv 3B_{7,11}(n) \pmod{11}. \tag{55}$$

By mathematical induction, Congruence (10) follows from (55). Employing (10) in (54), we obtain (11).

5. Congruence for (27, 11)-regular Bipartition

We now present a proof of Theorem 3.

Proof of Theorem 3. Setting $s = 27$, and $t = 11$ in (6), we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{27,11}(n)q^n = \frac{f_{27}f_{11}}{f_1^2} \equiv f_{27}f_1^9 \pmod{11}. \tag{56}$$

Substituting (17) into (56), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{27,11}(n)q^n &\equiv f_{27} (a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3)^3 \pmod{11} \\ &\equiv a(q^3)^3 f_3^3 f_{27} + 2qa(q^3)^2 f_3^2 f_9^3 f_{27} + 5q^2 a(q^3) f_3 f_9^6 f_{27} \\ &\quad + 6q^3 f_9^9 f_{27} \pmod{11}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{27,11}(3n)q^n \equiv a(q)^3 f_1^3 f_9 + 6qf_3^9 f_9 \pmod{11}. \tag{57}$$

Substituting (17) and (18) into (57), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{27,11}(3n)q^n &\equiv f_9 \left(a(q^3) + 6q \frac{f_9^3}{f_3} \right)^3 (a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3) + 6qf_9 \pmod{11} \\ &\equiv a(q^3)^4 f_3 f_9 + 6qf_3^9 f_9 + 4qa(q^3)^3 f_9^4 + 10q^2 \frac{a(q^3)^2 f_9^7}{f_3} \\ &\quad + 2q^3 \frac{a(q^3) f_9^{10}}{f_3^2} + q^4 \frac{f_9^{13}}{f_3^3} \pmod{11}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{27,11}(9n+3)q^n \equiv 6f_1^9 f_3 + 4a(q)^3 f_3^4 + q \frac{f_3^{13}}{f_1^3} \pmod{11}. \tag{58}$$

Substituting (17), (18) and (19) into (58), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{27,11}(9n+3)q^n &\equiv 6f_3 (a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3)^3 + 4f_3^4 \left(a(q^3) + 6q \frac{f_9^3}{f_3} \right)^3 \\ &\quad + qf_3^{13} \left(a^2(q^3) \frac{f_9^3}{f_3^{10}} + 3qa(q^3) \frac{f_9^6}{f_3^{11}} + 9q^2 \frac{f_9^9}{f_3^{12}} \right) \\ &\equiv 10a(q^3)^3 f_3^4 + 8qa(q^3)^2 f_3^3 f_9^3 + 3q^2 a(q^3) f_3^2 f_9^6 \\ &\quad + 7q^3 f_3 f_9^9 \pmod{11}. \end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

It follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{27,11}(27n+12)q^n \equiv 8a(q)^2 f_1^3 f_3^3 \pmod{11}. \tag{60}$$

Substituting (17) and (18) into (60), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{27,11}(27n+12)q^n &\equiv 8f_3^3 \left(a(q^3) + 6q \frac{f_9^3}{f_3} \right)^2 (a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3) \\ &\equiv 8a(q^3)^3 f_3^4 + 6qa(q^3)^2 f_3^3 f_9^3 + 5q^3 f_3 f_9^9. \end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

It follows that

$$B_{27,11}(81n+66) \equiv 0 \pmod{11} \tag{62}$$

and

$$B_{27,11}(81n+39) \equiv 9B_{27,11}(27n+12) \pmod{11}. \tag{63}$$

By (62) and (63), the proof is complete.

6. Congruence for (243, 17)-regular Bipartition

We now present a proof of Theorem 4.

Proof of Theorem 4. Setting $s = 243$, and $t = 17$ in (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{243,17}(n)q^n &= \frac{f_{243}f_{17}}{f_1^2} \\ &\equiv f_{243}f_1^{15} \pmod{17}. \end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

Substituting (17) into (64), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{243,17}(n)q^n &\equiv f_{243} (a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3)^5 \pmod{17} \\ &\equiv a(q^3)^5 f_3^5 f_{243} + 2qa(q^3)^4 f_3^4 f_9^3 f_{243} + 5q^2 a(q^3)^3 f_3^3 f_9^6 f_{243} \\ &\quad + 2q^3 a(q^3)^2 f_3^2 f_9^9 f_{243} + 14q^4 a(q^3) f_3 f_9^{12} f_{243} \\ &\quad + 12q^5 f_9^{15} f_{243} \pmod{17}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{243,17}(3n+2)q^n \equiv 5a(q^3)^3 f_1^3 f_3^6 f_{81} + 12q f_3^{15} f_{81} \pmod{17}. \tag{65}$$

Substituting (17) and (18) into (65), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{243,17}(3n+2)q^n &\equiv 5f_3^6 f_{81} \left(a(q^3) + 6q \frac{f_9^3}{f_3} \right)^3 (a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3) + 12q f_3^{15} f_{81} \\ &\equiv 5a(q^3)^4 f_3^7 f_{81} + 12q f_3^{15} f_{81} + 7qa(q^3)^3 f_3^6 f_9^3 f_{81} \\ &\quad + 15q^2 a(q^3)^2 f_3^5 f_9^6 f_{81} + 4q^3 a(q^3) f_3^4 f_9^9 f_{81} \\ &\quad + 7q^4 f_3^3 f_9^{12} f_{81} \pmod{17}. \end{aligned}$$

If we extract those terms in which the power of q is congruent to 1 modulo 3, dividing by q and replacing q^3 by q , then we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{243,17}(9n+5)q^n \equiv 12f_1^{15} f_{27} + 7a(q)^3 f_1^6 f_3^3 f_{27} + 7q f_1^3 f_3^{12} f_{27} \pmod{17}. \tag{66}$$

Substituting (17) and (18) into (66), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{243,17}(9n+5)q^n &\equiv 12 (a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3)^5 f_{27} \\ &\quad + 7 \left(a(q^3) + 6q \frac{f_9^3}{f_3} \right)^3 (a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3)^2 f_3^3 f_{27} \\ &\quad + 7q (a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3) f_3^{12} f_{27} \pmod{17} \\ &\equiv 2a(q^3)^5 f_3^5 f_{27} + 7qa(q^3) f_3^{13} f_{27} + 6qa(q^3)^4 f_3^4 f_9^3 f_{27} \\ &\quad + 13q^2 f_3^{12} f_9^3 f_{27} + 4q^2 a(q^3)^3 f_3^3 f_9^6 f_{27} + 4q^3 a(q^3)^2 f_3^2 f_9^9 f_{27} \\ &\quad + 8q^4 a(q^3) f_3 f_9^{12} f_{27} + 16q^5 f_9^{15} f_{27} \pmod{17}. \end{aligned}$$

If we extract those terms in which the power of q is congruent to 2 modulo 3, dividing by q and replacing q^3 by q , then we have

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{243,17}(27n+23)q^n \equiv 13f_1^{12} f_3^3 f_9 + 4a(q)^3 f_1^3 f_3^6 f_9 + 16q f_3^{15} f_9 \pmod{17}.$$

Substituting (17) and (18) into (67), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{243,17}(27n+23)q^n &\equiv 13(a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3)^4 f_3^3 f_9 \\ &\quad + 4\left(a(q^3) + 6q\frac{f_9^3}{f_3}\right)^3 (a(q^3)f_3 - 3qf_9^3) f_3^6 f_9 + 16qf_3^{15} f_9 \\ &\equiv 16qf_3^{15} f_9 + 6qa(q^3)^3 f_3^6 f_9^4 + 8q^4 f_3^3 f_9^{13} \pmod{17}. \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 4, follow from (67).

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